

2-TOM, 1-SON

Gimnastikaning- ta'limni rivojlantiruvchi turlari

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Anatatsiya: Gimnastik mashqlarnig turfa xilligi ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarining yo'naltirilganligiga qarab, gimnastikaning mustaqil turlariga birlashtiriladi. 1984 yilda o'tgan Umumittifoq anjumanida quyidagi tasniflash tasdiqlangan: gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi, ta'limni- rivojlantiruvchi va sport turlari. Gimnastikaning ushbu turlariga quyidagilar kiradi: asosiy, ayollar, atletik va kasbiy-amaliyturlari.

Kalit so'z: Gimnastikaning ushbu turlariga quyidagilar kiradi: asosiy, ayollar, atletik va kasbiy-amaliy turlari.

Asosiy gimnastika sog'lomlashtirish, ta'lim va tarbiya vazifalarining yechimi uchun katta imkoniyatlarga ega. Ular mashqlarning ko'p tuzilishga egaligi va ko'p funksiyaligi hisobidan amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Bu shug'ullanuvchilarni maxsus bilimlar va ko'nikmalar tizimi bilan boyitishga, pedagogning ijodiy yondashuvi uchun cheksiz imkoniyatlarni ochib beradi. Bunday bilimlar gimnastika- bu sport-pedagogik fan haqidagi bilimlar bo'lishi mumkin: uning mazmuni, ijtimoiy ahamiyati, tarixi, uning negizida turgan mashqlar bajarilishining texnikasi va qonunlari; mashqlarni sog'lomlashtirish, ta'lim va tarbiya maqsadlarida qo'llash imkoniyatlari haqida, tanlangan o'quv, kasbiy yoki sport faoliyatiga qarab harakat va psixik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, organizmning alohida organlari va tizimlariga, ularning funksional imkoniyatlarini kuchaytirish maqsadida ta'sir qilish haqida, o'quvchilarni har tomonlama tajriba bilan boyitish, amaliy mashqlarni o'rgatish va b. Asosiy gimnastikaning mashqlari pedagog so'zi va musiqali kuzatuv bilan birgalikda samarali majmuiy vosita va shug'ullanuvchilarda shaxs fazilatlarini

tarbiyalash usuli: gimnastika mashg'ulotlariga, o'qishga, mehnat va jamoa faoliyatiga vijdonli, chuqur anglagan va faol munosabat. Jismonan va ruhan barkamol shaxsni rivojlantirish maqsadida asosiy gimnastikaning keng imkoniyatlarini qo'llash, uni barcha yoshdagi shug'ullanuvchilarning jismoniy tarbiya usuli va mustaqil

2-TOM, 1-SON

vositasiga aylantirgan. O'rta yoshdagi tizimli mashg'ulotlar uzoq muddatga jismoniy va aqliy ishga layoqatligini yuqori darajada saqlab turishga ko'maklashadi. Maktabda asosiy gimnastika jismoniy tarbiya darslariga kiritilgan, umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik, sog'lomlashtirish guruxlarida qo'llaniladi. Mashg'ulotlarda unga kiritilgan barcha mashqlar majmui qo'llaniladi.

Ayollar gimnastikasi- ayollar organizmining xususiyatlarini va psixologik tuzilishini inobatga oladi. Mashqlarni, metodik usullarini tanlashda, eng avvalo, onalik funksiyalari inobatga olinadi, shuning uchun kuchni, tezlikni, oyoqlar, qorin va orqa tomon mushaklarining chidamliligini rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Mashg'ulotlarga umumrivojlantiruvchi gimnastik mashqlarning barchasi kiritiladi: anjomlar bilan va anjomlarsiz erkin mashqlar, gimnastik devorchada, o'tirg'ichda bajariladigan mashqlar va b. Ayollar bilan mashg'ulotlarda badiiy gimnastika mashqlari, **tomosha** va xalq o'yinlari elementlari va musiqa katta ahamiyatga ega. Mashg'ulotlarning musiqali kuzatuviga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Ushbu mashqlar yordamida harakatlar **koordinatsiyasi**, jozibasi, go'zalligi rivojlanadi, to'g'ri va chiroyli qadi-qomat shakllanadi, sog'lik mustahkamlanadi, jismoniy va aqliy ishlarga layoqatlik darajasi ko'tariladi.

Kasbiy sohaga yo'naltirilgan gimnastika quyidagi mashqlarni va metodik usullarni birlashtiradi. Ular yordamida o'z vaqtida kasbiy ta'lim boshlangancha, organizmning funksional imkoniyatlarini ko'tarish, harakatlanish va psixik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish va o'rganish (baholash), shug'ullanuvchilarga tanlangan kasbiy faoliyatiga zarur bo'lgan shaxs xususiyatlarini tarbiyalashi mumkin. Kasbiy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishga va amaliy harakatlanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga o'rta maxsus va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida katta e'tibor qaratilgan. Haqiqatda butun jismoniy tayyorgarlik amaliy xarakterga ega, yoxud u shug'ullanuvchilar tanlagan mehnat faoliyatini muvafaqiyatli egallash va unda kasbiy mahoratga erishish uchun zarur bo'lgan qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan.

Atletik gimnastika- mushaklar kuchini, chidamlilikni va irodani, organizmning funksional imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish, o'smir va o'spirin o'g'il bolalarni doimiy jismoniy mashqlar mashg'ulotlariga jalb qilishning; sog'lom hayot tarzini shakllantirishning; tamaki chekish, narkotik moddalarni iste'mol qilish va sog'lik uchun zararli bo'lgan boshqa odatlarning oldini olish va shaxsni shakllantirishning; o'spirinlarni mehnatga, qiz juvonlarni onalikka tayyorlash uchun ajoyib vositasi va

2-TOM, 1-SON

usuli. Atletik gimnastika gigienik gimnastikaning davomi bo'lib, sport gimnastikaning boshlanishi bo'lishi mumkin.

Gimnastikaning sport turlari

Sport gimnastikasi- ko'p kurashli sport turi. Uning tarkibida: erkaklarda- erkin mashqlar, ot sport anjomida, xalqalarda, bruslarda, turnikda mashqlar, tayanch sakrashlar; ayollarda- tayanch sakrashlar, turli balandlikdagi bruslarda, gimnastik yog'ochda bajariladigan mashqlar vaerkin mashqlar. Sport gimnastikasi mashg'ulotlariga badiiy va ritmik gimnastika, akrobatika, xoreografiya, o'yin va b. mashqlar kiritiladi. Sport gimnastikasi- olimpiya sport turi. Bizning davlatimizda uni Sport gimnastika federasiyasi boshqaradi.

Badiiy gimnastika- faqat ayollar sport turidir. Uning asosiy vositalari anjomlar va

anjomlarsiz bajariladigan raqs xarakteriga ega mashqlar. Ular qiz bolalar va ayollar jismoniy tarbiyasining ajoyib vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ushbu sport turining bir qator elementlari jismoniy madaniyat bo'yicha maktab dasturiga kiritilgan. Yuqori sinflarda badiiy gimnastika bo'yicha mustaqil mashg'ulotlar o'tkaziladi. Badiiy gimnastika- olimpiya sport turlaridan biri.

Sport akrobatikasi uch guruhdagi mashqlarni o'ziga qamrab olgan: akrobatik sakrashlar, juftlikda (erkaklar va aralash juftliklar) va gurux mashqlari. Batutda bajariladigan mashqlarni akrobatik mashqlarga kiritadilar. Akrobatik mashqlar murakkabligining keng qamrovi turli jinsdagi, yoshdagi va har xil jismoniy tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lgan shaxslarni o'rgatish imkonini beradi.

Akrobatika mashg'ulotlari uchun murakkab sport jixozlari kerak emas, akrobatik yo'lakcha va gimnastik matlar bo'lsa yetarli. Mashg'ulotlarni faqat sport zalida emas, balki sport maydonchasida ham tashkil etsa bo'ladi.

Sport aerobikasi- ushbu sport turida sportchilar murakkab **koordinasion asiklik** harakatlar birliklarini, turli tuzilma guruxlarning har xil murakkablikdagi elementlarni, hamda sheriklarning o'zaro harakatlanishini o'ziga qamrab olgan uzuluksiz va yuqori samarali mashqlar majmuini bajaradilar. Quyidagi mashqlar turlarini o'ziga qamrab olgan: ayollar va erkaklarning individual chiqishlari, aralash juftliklar, har qanday tarkibdagi uchliklar va oltiliklar. Ushbu mashqlarda xoreografiya asosini "tayanch" aerob qadamlari va ularning birliklari tashkil etadi.

2-TOM, 1-SON

1995 yilda Xalqaro Olimpiya qo'mitasi aerobikani rasmiy sport turi deb tan olgan va u Xalqaro gimnastika federasiyasiga kiritildi.

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